

BRINGING TURBOMACHINERY AEROMECHANICS RESEARCH CLOSER TO EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

The paper presents experiences from an international student project course in turbomachinery aeromechanics, which has been established within the framework of the H2020 research project ARIAS (“Advanced Research Into Aeromechanical Solutions”). The main activities, challenges, and lessons learned from the students’ feedback and instructors’ experience from 2020 to 2022 are presented from an educational point of view. A key goal of the aeromechanic project course (APC) is to strengthen the link between education and research based on multinational collaborative work. The course focuses on gradually enabling the students to perform a forced response analysis within one academic semester. This is achieved by providing the necessary fundamentals as well as training and application of interdisciplinary tools to investigate structural and aerodynamic effects. The course is based on online lectures, tool-specific tutorials, literature reviews, and guest lectures. The students work via web-based communication in international teams conducting various numerical analyses to determine distinct influences on forced response phenomena at the ARIAS TUDa transonic compressor. Metrics regarding the course structure, quality, project rating, and students’ feedback are obtained via an anonymous survey. The shown collaborative results and conclusions presented by the students display that the gap between theoretical knowledge and application is reduced.

Keywords: aeromechanics, education, collaborative projects

NOMENCLATURE

APC	Aeromechanic Project Course
ARIAS	Advanced Research into Aeromechanical Solutions
EO	Engine Order
IC	Imperial College London
KTH	Kungliga Tekniska Högskolan - Royal Institute of Technology Stockholm
ND	nodal diameter
OP	operating point
PBL	problem-based and project-based learning
TUDa	Technical University of Darmstadt
UPM	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid
USTUTT	University of Stuttgart
VIGV	variable inlet guide vanes

1. INTRODUCTION

During the past decades, the benefits of problem-based and project-based learning (PBL) have been widely recognized and adopted in the practice of engineering education [1]. Both these learning concepts belong under the umbrella of student-centered learning models. According to [2] project-based learning begins with an assignment to carry out one or more tasks that lead to the production of a final product – a design, a model, a device, or a computer simulation. The culmination of the project is normally a written and/or oral report summarizing the procedure used to produce the product and presenting the outcome. According to this interpretation, a project is a narrowly formulated task while problem-based learning is more of an open-ended and ill-defined approach.

The need for project-based learning integrated in engineering education is highlighted by [3], explaining that the

industry requires graduates who are able to participate in engineering project organizations and collaborate. At the same time, the integration of research and teaching activities in universities has been supported by a growing demand from future employers (both academic institutions and industry) for problem-solvers with skills to undertake an enquiry. In the face of rapid advances and innovation across many fields of knowledge, it is also increasingly important to prepare students to be lifelong learners able to continue to learn after graduation [4].

Within the frame of the ARIAS research project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program, a joint effort has been made to set up a collaborative international project course in aeromechanics (APC). Throughout the course that spans over one academic semester (five months) and runs mostly online, the students from different academic partners are collaborating on a project work directly related to the ongoing research activities of the ARIAS project. Since its start in spring 2020, the course has been engaging between 15 and 25 MSc- and PhD-level students every year. The participating universities are the Royal Institute of Technology (KTH), Technical University of Darmstadt (TUDa), University of Stuttgart (USTUTT), Imperial College London (IC) and Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM). The overall approach, how the course is structured and samples of the results obtained by the students are described further in this paper.

2. METHODOLOGIES

The collaborative aeromechanics project course implements both research-based teaching, where students are undertaking actual research activities while carrying out the project work, and research-tutored teaching where they are engaged in discussions about existing research findings and practices (as defined in [4]). The overall APC layout is illustrated in Figure 1. The course starts with a series of lectures and tutorials to provide the students with the necessary knowledge prior to engaging in the project work. Guest lecturers from the industry and academia are invited to give an insight in state-of-the-art research methods and industrial practices concerning turbomachinery aeromechanics. The tutorials are tailored in such a way that students work in smaller groups on performing specific tasks constituting essential steps of a forced response analysis: static and modal analysis of a rotor blisk, steady-state aerodynamic analysis, aerodamping calculations, unsteady aerodynamic forcing simulations, and finally forced response analysis determining the blade vibration amplitudes and induced alternating stresses. The numerical analyses are performed using Ansys Workbench tool.

In parallel with tutorials and lectures, the students are carrying out an extensive literature review. This activity is also done as a group activity and each group is addressing a different topic by reviewing a number of scientific papers on the topic. The literature review exercise ends with a seminar where the groups are presenting the main findings to their peers. The aim

of the activity is to reflect on the research methods and findings of the papers and to train their presentation and communication skills. Additionally, it provides a profound overview of the current state-of-research in the field of aeromechanics.

FIGURE 1: COURSE LAYOUT

Once completing all the tutorials, the students are introduced to the project. The test case they analyze is a 1.5 stage high-pressure transonic compressor test rig at TUDa [5], as shown in Figure 2, where its rotor blisk is subjected to upstream wakes from a Variable Inlet Guide Vane (VIGV). The rig is currently being extensively used in the experimental campaign in work package 1 of the ARIAS project, focusing specifically on forced response in compressors.

In each edition of the project course that has been run so far, different parameters have been assessed by the students, as shown in Figure 2. Two resonance crossings have been identified in the experimental campaign as interesting points to analyze, namely EO8 Mode 2 and EO8 Mode 3 crossings. The choice of these was also partially governed by the fact that the students are limited by the Ansys student license capability with respect to the size of the numerical model. In the first edition of the course (APC2020), the students were looking into the impact of the VIGV stagger angle and trailing edge geometry on the forced response of the rotor blisk. In the second year (APC2021), the focus was on the effects of the tip gap and two different tip clearances were assessed. The most recent batch of students (APC2022) was looking into VIGV stagger angle variation, vane count, and axial position with respect to the rotor.

To analyze the impact of different geometrical features on vibration amplitudes of the compressor rotor blades, the students have to implement and carry out the entire forced response analysis chain, as illustrated in Figure 3.

FIGURE 2: DIFFERENT CONFIGURATIONS INVESTIGATED BY THE STUDENTS IN 2020-2022 COURSE EDITIONS

FIGURE 4: PHYSICAL APC WORKSHOP AT KTH

FIGURE 3: FORCED RESPONSE ANALYSIS CHAIN

Throughout the project work, emphasis is put on fostering international collaboration among the students. The students are therefore assigned to groups such that the multinational constellations are achieved. Such groups are different from the tutorial and literature review in order to diversify their interaction with one another. The groups are entirely self-organized and it is up to each group to define the way in which they split the work among themselves. The students have the freedom to present their results as they believe fit the purpose. A set of milestones have been designed during the project work timeline as a sanity check to achieve the intended goals. The project work ends with a final seminar where all student groups present in a consolidated way their project results to the researchers involved in the ARIAS project and other invited guests, with the freedom to present their results using their own criteria.

In the last course edition (APC 2022), a physical workshop was implemented as part of the course. This was enabled by the Erasmus + funding scheme for so called Blended Intensive Programs (BIP), where the students' and staff mobility is being promoted as an addition to the virtual course components. During a five-day workshop at KTH in Stockholm, the students had chance to interact face-to-face with each other and the course instructors. Apart from benefit of actually sitting closely with the other project group members, the students also had opportunity to meet the aeromechanics specialists from industries like Rolls-Royce, Siemens and GKN Aerospace AB. A set of relevant experimental activities has also been designed and implemented during the workshop, to provide some hands-on experience to the students.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Since the students are working on topics related to the research questions and experimentally investigated compressor configurations of ARiAS, some results indicate relevant trends and qualitative insights, highlighting interesting investigation targets for the research project partners. It also demonstrates the possibilities of performing comprehensive analysis with limited computational performance, for example considering the Ansys student license and numerical experience.

3.1 Samples of students results

The project topics varied between the courses (as shown in Figure 2), focusing on different variations in excitation and other potential influencing parameters. As the students had to develop and agree on analysis focus and methods, the results and especially the corresponding representation vary between the courses.

APC 2020 – IGV Stagger Variation

The results obtained by the students indicate that the de-staggering of the upstream VIGVs from 0° to 20° has a significant impact on the aerodynamic forcing and exhibits elevated excitation levels produced by the strong wakes that come from the de-staggered vanes. The rotor blade vibration amplitude is almost three times higher compared to the reference case at peak efficiency, as indicated in Figure 5. The presented aerodynamic damping for both configurations produced the same magnitude. This observation was considered for future years when assessing the damping.

FIGURE 5: SELECTED RESULTS OBTAINED BY THE STUDENTS IN 2020 COURSE EDITION

APC 2021 – Rotor Tip Gap Variation

Tip gap variation is shown to have a significant effect on the aerodynamic damping of the rotor blades. The impact of the tip gap on the vibration amplitude seems to depend on the corresponding mode shape and therefore the specific resonance crossing analyzed. Figure 6 illustrates the different investigated compressor speed lines and resulting aerodamping for selected operating points. For Mode 2 (1st torsion) ND8, the larger tip gap tends to lead to a lower aerodynamic damping and higher vibrational amplitudes compared to the smaller tip gap. The students attributed this to reinforced secondary flow phenomena in the tip region, which locally disturbs the aerodynamic wall work performed on the blade in regions of high modal displacement, hence decreasing the damping and increasing vibrational amplitudes of this specific resonance, at least over the range of the investigated operating points. For Mode 3 (2nd bending) ND8, the situation seems to be the opposite. Predicted vibrational amplitudes for the large tip gap OPs are smaller than the amplitudes obtained for the small tip gap. This was in particular interesting since the aerodynamic damping was lower for two of the investigated large tip gap OPs (at peak efficiency and near choke conditions). Students explained these differences by showing unfavorable distribution of the unsteady blade pressure in relation to the vibration mode shape, causing high aerodynamic forcing in critical regions and as a result higher maximum blade deflections for the small tip gap configuration.

FIGURE 6: SELECTED RESULTS OBTAINED BY THE STUDENTS IN 2021 COURSE EDITION

APC 2022 – VIGV Configuration and Position Variation

The VIGVs configurations are the key driver for a different operational point in the compressor map as well as the analyzed modeshape. Figure 7 displays the compressor map for all analyzed cases including the aerodynamic damping, where solid lines represent N100 and dashed N79.5. Mode 2 showed higher aerodynamic damping with respect to Mode 3, with a tendency to increase towards near stall conditions. Similarly, the figure displays the entropy gradients at 50% span between the stationary and rotatory components where the wakes are visualized better. The plots point out that a negative stagger produces a stronger shock, inducing numerical reflection waves in the rotor domain. The highest blade response is found at near stall conditions. For mode 2 is at the negative VIGVs stagger, whereas for Mode 3 is at the axial variation configuration.

FIGURE 7: SELECTED RESULTS OBTAINED BY THE STUDENTS IN 2022 COURSE EDITION

3.2 Students feedback

In order to get a feedback from the students and their suggestions for improvements, an anonymous course survey has been conducted after every course. Overall, the project rate feedback was very positive, with an average of 90% of the students rating from “good” to “very good” within APC2020 – APC2022.

The students appreciate the well-organized international project setting, providing a unique as well as challenging working environment with high-quality course content. The lectures, tutorials and project period allow a comprehensive overview of aeroelasticity with its interdisciplinary topics, both from a theoretical perspective as well as tool training and application. The guest lectures point toward real-world problems and inspire the students to study aeromechanics. Additionally, it provides good networking possibilities between the students, researchers, industry and universities. While running APC2020-APC2022 in a virtual mode, still enables a good collaboration within the course setting. The highlight of APC2022 was the physical workshop at KTH where students met and worked face-to-face, accompanied by live experiments in the laboratory and social events, which fostered the course learning outcomes and students’ experiences in a multi-national project.

The students also addressed some helpful suggestions for improvements with respect to general organization, course contents, arrangement of learning modules and international collaboration. For example, leading to more course phases with different internationally mixed groups or common “big-picture” research questions for the project within the subsequent APC. The students identified target-oriented post-processing as a major challenge, requesting additional and interactive lectures and tutorials, especially with respect to Ansys and corresponding analysis. In order to enhance the international collaboration, the students suggest having a face-to-face kick-off meeting at one of the partners, as well as the workshop period at the end of the project. Similarly, students from APC2022 acknowledge the complexity and challenges regarding workload distribution and data management for a coherent result presentation. This proved challenging as 23 students worked on a common project, where internal group leaders were selected for management purposes.

Ultimately, the students highly appreciate the opportunity of participating in this international and research-oriented course.

3.3 Lessons learned from the instructors’ point of view

The course was initiated by KTH and TUDa, both being part of the ARIAS project, resulting in a good and efficient collaboration, building the international, multi-university course based on an existing module within the THRUST master program at KTH. ARIAS enabled a helpful framework to include different partners from academia and industry, extending the actively participating universities and students as well as adding valuable guest lectures from the turbomachinery community. The lessons learned and students’ feedback helped to improve the course continuously, ultimately resulting in a comprehensive learning module with virtual and in-person components. A metric of the course organization and quality was assessed within

the anonymous survey. The results show an increase of “fully agree” and “agree” that the course was well structured, from 65% in APC2020 to 92% in APC2022. Similarly, the APC showed consistent growth in students’ intake starting with 15 in the first intake to 26 in the most recent one.

Nevertheless, organizing an international, multi-university project course offers some challenges. On the one hand, the course contents and related modules (combination of lectures, tutorials and project periods) have to fit into the individual university curricula and be rewarded with the corresponding credits. This appeared to be a huge issue for other universities, interested to participate in the APC. Study programs should provide certain flexibility to initiate new types of courses, such as the APC, without multiple years of preparation. On the other hand, the different semester schedules make it difficult to run a five-month course without, for example, colliding with exam periods. A varying number of participating partners and groups of students with different academic backgrounds complicates the organization. Also, providing suitable and comparable hardware resources and accessibility for large numbers of students at different universities, running multiple days of simulations and its corresponding data storage has to be considered. It is important to have a rough estimation of the computational effort that implies all these simulations, to make it feasible for the students. Figure 8 quantifies these simulation times, where the transient CFD simulation is the one considered the bottleneck for the forced response analysis chain. Overall, approximately 24 days of computational time is needed for all the analyses (here exemplarily shown for APC2020). Using the Ansys student license was helpful to contain the computational time and data storage while fulfilling the intended learning outcomes.

FIGURE 8: ESTIMATION OF THE COMPUTATIONAL EFFORT

The inherent virtual mode of the course to smooth out the challenges mentioned previously proved to be a key strength. During the COVID-19 pandemic, the overall APC was not affected. An additional benefit of the APC from the instructors’ perspective is that it has served as a pool to identify outstanding students. The course has worked as an indirect recruit mechanism for research engineering/PhD candidacies in the aeromechanics field.

Ultimately, organizing and running the APC was a rewarding experience for all participants, providing fruitful collaborations and networking opportunities between different partners from universities and industry. Furthermore, it is a

valuable addition to a typical research-oriented project such as ARIAS.

4. CONCLUSIONS

An international collaborative student project course in aeromechanics is presented and the main activities are highlighted. The course focuses on turbomachinery aeromechanics, necessary fundamentals as well as training and application of interdisciplinary tools to investigate structural and aerodynamic effects. It includes lectures, tool-specific tutorials, literature reviews, and guest lectures. The students work via web-based communication in multi-national teams conducting various simulations to determine distinct influences on forced response phenomena at the ARIAS TUDa transonic compressor. The shown collaborative results and conclusions presented by the students display that the gap between theoretical knowledge and application gap is reduced.

The course combines research and project-oriented learning in an international environment and strengthens the education of next-generation engineers and researchers. The overall project frame and goals are summarized in Figure 9. So far, similar course formats are not established in the European turbomachinery aeroelastic community, and the student survey feedback has emphasized the importance of versatile projects, as accomplished by the continuously expanding and improving APC.

FIGURE 9: GENERAL PROJECT FRAME AND GOALS OF APC

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